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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION - INGREDIENTS OF *TRIKARSHIKA*

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Abstract

Now a days, the demand of Herbal pharmaceutical products has been surged up. To compensate the demand of herbal products, large quantity of raw material is needed. To fulfil this demand sometimes non intentionally or deliberately adulteration or substitution is done. So, to make sure the quality of raw material as well as products, analysis is important. Here, the powder microscopy plays the important role for authentication of herbal drug. **Material & Method:** Powder microscopy of *Trikarshika* was carried out. *Trikarshika* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle) and *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.). Slides of each ingredient of *Trikarshika* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Trikarshika* shows fragments of fibers, tissue cell, vessel element, oleoresin cell, starch grains. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Trikarshika* helps in the correct identification of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle) and *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.). Powder microscopy is one of the easiest methods which helps in quality control and assurance of herbal drug

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INTRODUCTION:

Now a days the use of herbal drugs in global market has been extensively used in every sector i.e., pharmaceutical, cosmeceuticals, nutraceutical, etc. To compensate the demand of herbal products, large quantity of raw material is needed. To fulfil this demand sometimes unknowingly or knowingly adulteration or substitution is done. So, to keep a check on this and to achieve good therapeutic efficacy, analysis of raw material is vital. Powder is the simplest, easiest and most economical way for the authentication as well as standardization of the herbal drug.

Here, for the present study *Trikarshika* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Trikarshika* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved mentioned in Raj Nighantu.¹ It contains *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe. Family - Zingiberaceae), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle Family - Ranunculaceae) and *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn. Family - Cyperaceae).

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Trikarshika*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as fibres, tissues, vascular bundles, starch grains, etc. in the powder of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle) and *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.).
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Trikarshika was used for the powder microscopy. *Trikarshika* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle) and *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.). Rhizome of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.), *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle) and *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn.) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Trikarshika* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference¹⁻³

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No.: Powder microscopic characters found in *Trikarshika*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Sunthi</i>	<i>Ativisha</i>	<i>Musta</i>
1.	Fragments of fibres	+	+	-
2.	Tissue cell	+	+	+
3.	Vessel element	+	+	+
4.	Oleoresin cell	+	-	-

5.	Starch Grains	+	+	-
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Table No.: Powder microscopic study of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Sunthi</i>	Figure no.
1.	Cork in surface view	Fig. 1
2.	Reticulated vessel with pigment cells	Fig. 2
3.	Fibers	Fig. 3
4.	Starch grains	Fig. 4
5.	Fragment of fibres with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel	Fig. 4
6.	Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains	Fig. 5

Table No.: Powder microscopic study of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ativisha</i>	Figure no.
1.	Reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma	Fig. 1
2.	Starch grains	Fig. 2
3.	Fibers	Fig. 2
4.	Fragments of metaderm	Fig. 3
5.	Parenchyma cells filled with starch grains	Fig. 4

Table No.: Powder microscopic study of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Musta</i>	Figure no.
1.	Vessel element with spiral thickening	Fig. 1,2
2.	Tissue fragments with thin-walled cells	Fig. 3
3.	Starch Grains	Fig. 4

For the present study *Trikarshika* was selected. Powder microscopy of each ingredient of *Trikarshika* was done and information was gathered regarding the microscopic characters of each herbal drug. The microscopic characters of each ingredient of *Trikarshika* which were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.) shows, cork in surface view, reticulated vessel with pigment cells, fibers, starch grains, fragment of fibers and oleoresin cell. Powder microscopy of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle) shows reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma, starch grains, fibers, fragments of metaderm and parenchyma cells filled with starch grains. Powder microscopy of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn) shows vessel element with vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue fragments with thin-walled cells and starch grains.

Though it is very troublesome to standardize the compound formulations of Ayurved, it is fundamental requirement for guaranteeing the quality and safety of herbal drugs. Thus, making herbal drugs viable for the use in public domain. In this present study, powder microscopy of each ingredient of *Trikarshika* was carried out and their microscopic characters were noted. These characters might offer assistance in identifying impurities and exact identification of material available from the market.

Powder microscopic study of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.)

Fig. 1

Cork in surface view

Reticulated vessel with pigment cells

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fiber

Starch grains

Fragment of fibres with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains

Powder microscopic study of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle)

Fig 1

Fig 2

Fig 3

Fig 4

Powder microscopic study of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn)

Fig 1

Vessel element with spiral thickening

Fig 2

Fig 3

Tissue fragments with thin-walled cells

Fig 12

Starch Grain

CONCLUSION:

In the present study, powder microscopy of the well-known formulation i.e. *Trikarshika* was carried out. The findings provide assistance in the identification of each ingredient of *Trikarshika*. According to the observations, microscopic characters such as cork in surface view, reticulated vessel with pigment cells, fibers, starch grains, fragment of fibers and oleoresin cell indicates the presence of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.). Microscopic characters such as reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma, starch grains, fibers, fragments of metaderm and parenchyma cells filled with starch grains indicates the presence of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle). Microscopic characters such as vessel element with vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue fragments with thin-walled cells and starch grains indicates the presence of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn). Any other microscopic character if present or missing other than which are observed then there maybe the chance of adulteration in the compound. Thus, powder microscopy of herbal drug helps to identify the drugs by their histological characters.

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